

ECONOMIC REFORMS IN THE CONSTRUCTION FIELD

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Abstract: The reform of the construction economy is a component of the reform of the national economy. The state allows to choose priority directions for reforming the construction economy.

Key words: Market economy, mechanism, Investment, construction projects, design, engineering-research works, construction works

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the economy operates in the conditions of market relations. Since the first days of independence of Uzbekistan, the issue of transitioning the economy from the planned system to the basis of market relations has been raised and it has been started to be solved.

From the research published today, we can see that the market is a place where the producer (seller) and the consumer (buyer) meet, and that the market economy is a developing system, in which there is an abundance of consumer goods, their former we learned that it is produced mainly by the producers themselves, not only by the state, as in the past, but with the support of the state in necessary cases. As you can see, although this issue seems simple at first glance, it is quite complicated. The market economy has existed for more than three hundred years. During this period, it is constantly developing, improving, and adapting to the changing conditions in the life of society. For this reason, the market today is not at all like the market in Adam Smith's time or the one described in Karl Marx's Capital. But the basis of the market remained almost unchanged

METHOD RECOMMENDATIONS

The establishment and operation of the market economy is carried out in compliance with certain principles. Before describing their content, it should be said that the

structure of the market economy includes not only the market of goods and services where the producer (seller) meets the consumer (buyer), but also the market of financial resources (capital) and others. All these markets complement each other and form a mechanism of a single market economy. The characteristic features of this mechanism are as follows:

- freedom of communication between producers and consumers of products (works, services);
- freedom to choose partners;
- competition between market participants. According to the famous economist Leontev, the market mechanism is based on competition, but under the strict control of the state, it operates in connection with the systems of social services, which include a large part of the national income.

Instead of strictly centralized planning, it envisages indicative indicative planning. In other words, the market mechanism, like any other mechanism, needs to be properly managed and regulated

Technical and economic feasibility studies and other necessary documents of investment projects must undergo appropriate expertise before approval by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Selection of investment and construction projects is becoming one of the most important points in the organization and management of the construction complex. It is especially widely used in the following cases:

- design, engineering-research works, construction works, etc.;
- in the construction and technical re-equipment of production and non-production buildings and structures, enterprises, including handover as "lock and key";
- in the delivery of complete technological equipment and other labor tools;
- in project management, consultancy, supervision.

In order to increase the effectiveness of tenders and to strengthen competition in the contract market, it is envisaged that foreign design and construction companies will participate in this market in compliance with special rules and requirements.

That is, the construction complex, like the entire economy, has lost its previous "closed" status and is becoming open to foreign investors within the framework of the country's legislation. In this regard, the expertise and role of experts in investment projects is becoming stronger. Experts must have the necessary professional knowledge, experience and professional intuition. In foreign practice, the opinion of experts is usually not revised or even discussed. Specialists of management bodies, scientists, employees of research and design organizations, leaders in various fields can participate as experts in our conditions. The task of the experts is to conduct an initiative-logical analysis and check the calculations made in the project. The conclusion of experts can be the basis for participation in the tender for project development

CONCLUSION

The reform of the construction economy is a component of the reform of the national economy. The state allows to choose priority directions for reforming the construction economy. The state and indicators of the network economy show that construction lags far behind other sectors in terms of the implementation of full market mechanisms. Also, the formation of the class of property owners is slow, there are no large private construction companies, business activity has not yet reached the required pace and scale, and there is still no serious competition between construction organizations (companies). Today, the construction complex, which is becoming more and more independent in the management of the economy, and first of all its production links, must be reconstructed: abandon the principles of waiting for orders from "above", as before, self-sufficiency and transition to self-sufficiency is necessary. Increasing the efficiency of construction envisages the development of initiative and entrepreneurship, the rational integration of large, medium and small construction enterprises and organizations.

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